

1 **Testing the effect of combining innovative extraction technologies on the biological activities**
2 **of obtained β -glucan-enriched fractions from *Lentinula edodes***

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13 **Keywords:** β -glucan; shiitake mushroom; ultrasound-assisted extraction; subcritical water
14 extraction; hypocholesterolemic activity; immunomodulatory activity.

15 **Abbreviations:** HWE (hot water extraction), SPE (steam pressurized extraction), UAE
16 (ultrasound-assisted extraction), SWE (subcritical water extraction), SFE (supercritical fluid
17 extraction), MAE (microwave-assisted extraction), HPSEC (high-performance size-exclusion
18 chromatography system), HMGGR (3-hydroxy-3-methylglutaryl coenzyme A reductase).

19 **Abstract**

20 Innovative technologies as ultrasound-assisted extraction (UAE) (550W, 60% amplitude,
21 50°C) or subcritical water extraction (SWE) (200°C, 11.7 MPa) were more effective than hot water
22 extractions to obtain β -glucan-enriched fractions from shiitake mushrooms. UAE required longer
23 extraction time (60 min) than SWE (15 min). Combination of UAE+SWE or pre-treatment of the
24 raw material with supercritical CO₂ (SFE) (40°C, 35 MPa, 3h) before both extractions yielded
25 extracts containing larger β -glucan concentrations. Fluorimetric/colorimetric determinations
26 indicated that obtained fractions contained (1 \rightarrow 3)- and (1 \rightarrow 3),(1 \rightarrow 6)- β -glucans. NMR confirmed
27 their presence as well as (1 \rightarrow 3)- α -glucans and heteropolymers including mannose and galactose.
28 SWE (15 min), SFE+SWE or UAE+SWE extracts showed larger glucose levels and lower mannose
29 and galactose residues than the other extractions suggesting certain extraction specificity towards β -
30 glucans. They also included more chitin-derivatives than UAE. The extracts obtained after
31 combination of technologies partially retained their immunomodulatory properties but they showed
32 high hypocholesterolemic activities according to *in vitro* studies.

33 **1. Introduction**

34 *Lentinula edodes* is an Asian edible mushroom consumed worldwide and commonly known as
35 shiitake mushroom. Traditionally, it was included in popular remedies to prevent diseases or to
36 promote health and wellbeing and, in the last decades, scientific studies confirmed that indeed, the
37 mushroom contains many bioactive compounds that might reduce the risk of harmful disorders such
38 as cancer, cardio- or cerebrovascular diseases etc. (Khan, Gani, Khanday, & Massodi, 2018).
39 Fungal β -glucans are compounds thoroughly investigated because they are considered as dietary
40 fiber (together with chitins) with anti-inflammatory, immunomodulatory, antioxidant, anti-tumoral,
41 hypocholesterolemic, antimicrobial activities, etc. (Abreu et al., 2019; Bai et al., 2019; Caz et al.,
42 2016; Friedman, 2016; Khan et al., 2018; Zhang, Li, Wang, Zhang, & Cheung, 2011) and therefore,
43 they might be used to design novel functional foods.

44 Mushroom β -glucans are structurally different than those from plants or bacteria since they
45 have a main chain of β -D-glucose units (1 \rightarrow 3)-linked with different branching usually at O-6
46 position by β -D-glucose units or other oligosaccharides. Their branching degree determines the
47 tertiary structure of the glucan: (1 \rightarrow 3)- β -glucans with few or no branches mainly present a single
48 linear structure while highly branched (1 \rightarrow 3),(1 \rightarrow 6)- β -glucans show a triple helix conformation
49 (Nitschke et al., 2011). In shiitake mushrooms, lentinan is the major (1 \rightarrow 3),(1 \rightarrow 6)- β -glucan and
50 showed many beneficial properties for human health (Kupfahl, Geginat, & Hof, 2006; Suzuki,
51 Takatsuki, Maeda, Hamuro, & Chihara, 1994). Since the integrity of the molecules is important to
52 keep many of their beneficial properties, the extraction methods utilized to generate β -glucan-
53 enriched extracts should be carefully selected because they might modify their molecular weight or
54 tridimensional structure (Benito-Roman, Martin-Cortes, Cocero, & Alonso, 2016b).

55 Although some fungal polysaccharides are polar and easily extractable with water, many β -
56 glucans require aggressive treatments such as hot water or alkaline solutions and others remain in
57 the insoluble residue (Morales, Smiderle, Piris, Soler-Rivas, & Prodanov, 2019; Ruthes, Smiderle,
58 & Iacomini, 2015). Moreover, chitins are water insoluble polymers and only low molecular weight
59 derivatives or degradation products could be extracted using conventional hot water procedures

60 (Morales, Piris, Ruiz-Rodriguez, Prodanov, & Soler-Rivas, 2018a; Morales et al., 2019; Ruthes et
61 al., 2015). To obtain chitinous materials, more drastic treatments are required to induce dissolving
62 of other components in alkaline or acid solutions and the precipitation of chitin-enriched fractions
63 (Wu, Zivanovic, Draughon, & Sams, 2004; Wu, Zivanovic, Draughon, Conway, & Sams, 2005).
64 Novel advanced technologies such as ultrasound-assisted extractions (UAE) or subcritical water
65 extraction (SWE) facilitate the extraction of these and other polysaccharides using water as non-
66 pollutant solvent (Rosello-Soto et al., 2016, Maric et al., 2018). Ultrasound-assisted extractions
67 generates ultrasonic waves provoking implosions of the generated cavitation bubbles, causing
68 disruption of fungal cell walls. This treatment enhanced mass transfer and extraction yields (Chemat
69 et al., 2016; Morales, Ruiz-Rodriguez, & Soler-Rivas, 2018b, Rosello-Soto et al., 2015) and it was
70 successfully used to extract polysaccharides from several mushrooms (*Ganoderma lucidum*,
71 *Agaricus bisporus*, *Boletus edulis*, etc.) and their by-products (Aguilo-Aguayo, Walton, Vinas, &
72 Tiwari, 2017; Alzorqi, Sudheer, Lu, Manickam, 2017; Morales et al., 2018b). Pressurized liquid
73 extractions constitute other interesting approach to enhance polysaccharide extraction, particularly
74 SWE. When subcritical pressures are used, the solvent is heated above its boiling point keeping its
75 liquid state and conferring it different properties than those showed at room temperature and
76 atmospheric pressure. SWE modify dielectric constant of water and decrease its viscosity being able
77 to solubilize non-polar compounds such as large size polysaccharides (when temperature is above
78 100 °C) (Li, Dobruchowska, Gerwig, Dijkhuizen, & Kamerling, 2013; Plaza & Turner, 2015;
79 Smiderle et al., 2017; Morales et al., 2018b). Mushrooms polysaccharide-enriched extracts were
80 obtained by SWE from many species such as *Agaricus bisporus*, *Pleurotus ostreatus*, *Ganoderma*
81 *lucidum*, etc. (Palanisamy et al., 2014; Kodama et al., 2015; Smiderle et al., 2017).

82 Besides the previously mentioned, other green technologies were used to extract interesting
83 compounds from edible mushrooms. Supercritical fluid extractions (SFE), particularly those using
84 supercritical CO₂ as solvent, were mainly applied to selectively extract lipids from food matrices
85 because of the low polarity of the solvent (Herrero, Cifuentes, & Ibáñez, 2006). Therefore, it might
86 also be used to remove fat components from fungal extracts enhancing, in a subsequent step,

87 polysaccharide extraction, as described in previous works for *Antrodia camphorata* and *Agaricus*
88 *blazei* mycelia (Chen et al., 2007; Ker et al., 2005). Combinations of different extraction
89 technologies to obtain β -glucan-enriched extracts were also tested and higher yields than single
90 extractions were usually noticed. For instance, in a complex extraction reactor, the use of
91 pressurized hot water combined with sub/supercritical CO₂ increased 1.26 folds β -glucan yields
92 obtained from *Ganoderma lucidum* than using only pressurized hot water (Benito-Roman, Alonso,
93 Cocero, & Goto, 2016a). Moreover, ultrasonic/microwave assisted extractions (UMAE) were also
94 more effective than hot water extractions to obtain bioactive polysaccharides from *Inonotus*
95 *obliquus* (Chen, Huang, Li, Wang, & Tang, 2010) and combined with enzymes facilitated the
96 extraction even more (Yin, Fan, Fan, Shi, & Gao, 2018).

97 Therefore, in this work, UAE and SWE were firstly carried out at different extraction times to
98 define the most adequate to obtain β -glucan-enriched extracts from shiitake mushrooms. The
99 extraction yields were compared with more conventional extractions. Afterwards, combinations of
100 UAE and SWE as well as pre-treatments with SFE were investigated as innovative protocols to
101 improve β -glucan extraction yields. The nature of bioactive polysaccharides from the extracts was
102 determined by different methodologies (enzymatic and colorimetric methods, HPSEC, GC-MS,
103 NMR) and their biological activities studied *in vitro* (hypocholesterolemic and immunomodulatory
104 activities) to investigate whether the extraction procedure modify their beneficial properties.

105 **2. Materials and Methods**

106 ***2.1. Biological material***

107 Powdered *Lentinula edodes* S. (Berkeley) fruiting bodies (particle size < 0.5 mm, moisture
108 < 5%) were purchased from Glucanfeed S.L. (La Rioja, Spain) and stored in darkness at -20 °C until
109 further use.

110 ***2.2. Reagents***

111 Absolute ethanol and sulfuric acid (H₂SO₄) were obtained from Panreac and phenol, sodium
112 borohydride (NaBH₄), sodium hydroxide pellets, glycine, D-glucose, glucosamine hydrochloride,

113 aniline blue diammonium salt 95%, hydrochloric acid 37%, acetylacetone, p-
114 dimethylaminobenzaldehyde, trifluoroacetic acid, pyridine, acetic anhydride, copper(II) sulfate
115 (CuSO₄), deuterated dimethylsulfoxide (Me₂SO-d₆), Congo Red, citric acid, RPMI 1640 medium
116 and phorbol 12-myristate 13-acetate (PMA) were purchased from Sigma-Aldrich Quimica (Madrid,
117 Spain). CO₂ was supplied by Air-Liquid, S.A. (Madrid, Spain), schizophyllan was obtained from
118 Contipro Biotech (Dolni Dobrouc, Czech Republic) and synthetic soluble starch was acquired from
119 Scharlab (Barcelona, Spain).

120 ***2.3. Supercritical CO₂ extraction pre-treatment (SFE)***

121 Shiitake powder (253 g) was mixed with 1.9 kg of 6 mm diameter stainless steel spheres (ratio
122 1:1 (v/v) powder:spheres) in a 2 L extraction cell connected to a supercritical fluid extraction plant
123 (model SF2000, TharTechnology, Pittsburgh, PA). Pressurized CO₂ was applied into the loaded cell
124 at 35 MPa and 40 °C with a 3.6 kg/h recirculating flow during a total extraction time of 3 h as they
125 were the conditions described as adequate for fungal lipids (Morales et al., 2017; Morales et al.,
126 2018a). The lipophilic material solubilized in supercritical CO₂ was removed in separators (Garcia-
127 Risco, Vicente, Reglero, & Fornari, 2011). After those 3h, the pressurized material remaining in the
128 extraction cell (called SFE fraction) was separated from steel spheres by sieving in a sieve shaker
129 (Cisa BA200 N, Barcelona, Spain) and stored at -20 °C until further use.

130 ***2.4. Ultrasound-assisted extractions (UAE)***

131 Shiitake powder (1 g) was mixed in MilliQ water (100 mL) and submitted to sonication
132 (Branson SFX550 Digital Sonifier 550W, Branson Ultrasonics, USA) using an ultrasonic probe
133 (1/2'') and selecting 60% amplitude for sonication output. During processing, the temperature was
134 maintained at 50 °C using a water bath with ice and a thermometer and samples were taken after 15,
135 30, 45 and 60 min extraction in duplicate. The obtained mixtures were submitted to vacuum
136 filtration (through Whatman filter paper no. 1) to separate the soluble fraction from the insoluble
137 residue. Afterwards, soluble fractions were lyophilized (UAE fractions) using a freeze-dryer

138 LyoBeta 15 (Telstar, Madrid, Spain) and stored at -20 °C until they were further processed to obtain
139 polysaccharide-enriched extracts or submitted to subcritical water extractions.

140 The UAE fractions were mixed with water (50 g/L) and three volumes of ethanol to induce
141 polysaccharide precipitation and left incubating overnight at 4 °C. The precipitates were collected
142 by centrifugation (10 000 rpm, 10 min, 4 °C) in a Thermo Scientific Heraeus Multifuge (Thermo
143 Fisher Scientific, Madrid, Spain) and freeze-dried. The obtained polysaccharide-enriched extracts
144 (UAE extracts) were stored at -20°C until further analysis.

145 ***2.5. Subcritical water extractions (SWE)***

146 Shiitake powder (0.5 g) was mixed with washed sea sand (Panreac, Barcelona, Spain) at ratio
147 1:8 (mushroom:sand, w/w) and placed in an extraction cell (11 mL) covered with cellulose filters
148 (Dionex Corporation, USA) from an Accelerated Solvent Extractor (ASE) 350 (Dionex
149 Corporation, USA). Extractions were carried out in duplicate with MilliQ water at 200 °C and 11.7
150 MPa but using different extraction times (15, 30, 45 and 60 min). Temperature was fixed at 200 °C
151 as it was previously pointed as the ideal temperature to extract polysaccharides from shiitake
152 mushrooms (Palanisamy et al., 2014). The obtained mixtures were vacuum filtrated and the soluble
153 fractions were freeze-dried (SWE fractions) and used to generate polysaccharide-enriched extracts
154 (SWE extracts) as above described.

155 ***2.6. Conventional extractions***

156 Two different conventional extraction methods were followed to compare with the previously
157 mentioned advanced technologies. One was a simple hot water extraction (HWE) and the other was
158 a method frequently used to obtain polysaccharides using an autoclave (steam pressurized
159 extraction, SPE).

160 Shiitake powder (0.5 g) was mixed in MilliQ water (50 mL), placed into a water bath at 100 °C
161 and vigorously stirred during 15, 30, 45 and 60 min. Incubations were carried out in duplicate.
162 Afterwards, the obtained mixtures were vacuum filtrated and the soluble fractions freeze-dried.

163 Obtained HWE fractions were later submitted to polysaccharide extraction as previously described
164 to obtain hot water extracts (HWE extracts).

165 Similarly, the same shiitake mixture was heated at 120 °C for 20 min in an autoclave and cooled
166 down to 4 °C following the method reported by Jeurink, Noguera, Savelkoul, & Wichers (2008).
167 After the steam pressurized extraction (SPE), the mixture was also submitted to vacuum filtration
168 and the soluble fraction freeze-dried (SPE fraction) and further processed to obtain SPE extracts as
169 above indicated for HWE extracts.

170 ***2.7. Combined extractions***

171 Sequential extractions were also tested as indicated in Figure 1 by combining SFE pre-treatment
172 (35 MPa, 40°C, 3h) with ultrasound assisted extraction or subcritical water extraction. Thus,
173 obtained SFE fraction was submitted to UAE (550W, 50°C, 60% amplitude) during 60 min as
174 previously indicated for shiitake powder to generate a new SFE+UAE fraction that was further
175 processed to obtain a polysaccharide-enriched extract (SFE+UAE extract) as also described for
176 UAE extracts. Similarly, SFE fraction was submitted to SWE (200°C, 11.7 MPa, 15 min) obtaining
177 a SFE+SWE fraction and a SFE+SWE polysaccharide-enriched extract (SFE+SWE extract).
178 Moreover, the UAE fractions (550W, 50°C, 60% amplitude) obtained after 60 min sonication were
179 also submitted to subcritical water extraction (200°C, 11.7 MPa) during 15 min to obtain the
180 UAE+SWE fractions. Afterwards, polysaccharide-enriched extracts (UAE+SWE extracts) were also
181 generated following the same procedure as previously described for UAE extracts. All these
182 combined extracts were prepared in duplicate and stored as indicated for the simple extracts.

183 ***2.8. Determination of carbohydrates***

184 Total carbohydrate content of shiitake, the extracted fractions and the obtained polysaccharide-
185 enriched extracts was determined by the phenol-sulfuric acid method as described in Fox & Robyt
186 (1991).

187 Total β -glucan concentration was determined in the polysaccharide-enriched extracts using a
188 mushroom and yeast specific β -glucan determination kit (β -glucan Assay Kit Megazyme [®],
189 Megazyme, Wicklow, Ireland) following the instructions of the user's manual. Samples absorbance
190 was measured using a Genesys 10 UV spectrophotometer (Thermo Fisher Scientific, Madrid,
191 Spain).

192 The amount of (1 \rightarrow 3)- β -glucans in the extracts was determined by the fluorimetric method
193 described by Ko & Lin (2004) but including the modifications of Gil-Ramirez, Smiderle, Morales,
194 Iacomini, & Soler-Rivas (2019) and Smiderle et al. (2017). The measurements were performed in a
195 M200 Plate Reader (Tecan, Mannedorf, Switzerland) with excitation and emission wavelengths set
196 at 398 and 502 nm respectively. The (1 \rightarrow 3),(1 \rightarrow 6)- β -glucan content of the extracts was analyzed
197 following the colorimetric method (523 nm) described by Nitschke et al. (2011). Schizophyllan was
198 used as standard for both determinations.

199 Chitin content was determined according to Smiderle et al. (2017). Briefly, precipitated extracts
200 were hydrolyzed with 6 M HCl at 100 °C for 2 h. After the hydrolysis, samples were cooled down
201 and adjusted to pH 10.0. Then, hydrolyzed samples (250 μ L) were treated as described by
202 Rementeria et al. (1991) and absorbance was measured at 530 nm. A glucosamine hydrochloride
203 standard curve was used for quantification.

204 ***2.9. GC-MS analyses***

205 The monosaccharide composition of the polysaccharide-enriched extracts was determined by
206 hydrolyzing the extracts (1 mg) with 2M trifluoroacetic acid at 100 °C for 8 h followed by
207 evaporation to dryness. The dried samples were dissolved in distilled water (100 μ L) and NaBH₄ (1
208 mg) was added. Then, solution was kept at room temperature overnight to reduce aldose into
209 alditols (Sasaki et al., 2008) and later, the samples were dried and the NaBH₄ excess was
210 neutralized by adding acetic acid and then removed with methanol (twice) under a compressed air
211 stream. Alditols acetylation was performed in pyridine-acetic anhydride (200 μ L; 1:1 v/v) for 30
212 min at 100 °C. Pyridine was removed by washing with 5% CuSO₄ solution and the resulting alditol

213 acetates were extracted with chloroform. The samples were injected into an SH-Rtx-5ms (30 m x
214 0.25 mm ID x 0.25 μ m thickness phase). The column was connected to a GC-2010 Plus gas
215 chromatograph (Shimadzu, Kyoto, Japan) equipped with a Combipal autosampler (AOC 5000) and
216 coupled to a triple quadrupole mass spectrometer TQ 8040. The injector and ion source were held at
217 250 °C and helium at 1 mL/min was used as carrier gas. The oven temperature was programmed
218 from 100 to 280 °C at 10 °C/min with a total analysis time of 30 min. The samples were prepared in
219 hexane with 1 μ L being injected with a split ratio of 1:10. The mass spectrometer was operated in
220 the full-scan mode over a mass range of m/z 50-500 before selective ion monitoring mode, both
221 with electron ionization at 70 eV. Selective ion monitoring mode was used for quantification and
222 *GCMS solution* software (Tokyo, Japan) was used for data analysis. The obtained monosaccharides
223 were identified by their typical retention time compared to commercial available standards. Results
224 were expressed as mol%, calculated according to Pettolino, Walsh, Fincher, & Bacic (2012).

225 **2.10. HPSEC analyses**

226 Polysaccharide-enriched extracts were injected into a high-performance size-exclusion
227 chromatography system (HPSEC) (Waters, Massachussets, USA) coupled to refractive index
228 detector (Waters). Four gel-permeation Ultrahydrogel columns in series with exclusion sizes of
229 7×10^6 , 4×10^5 , 8×10^4 and 5×10^3 Da were used. The eluent was 0.1 aqueous NaNO₂ containing 200
230 ppm aqueous NaN₃ at 0.6 mL/min. The extracts were dissolved in the eluent (1 mg/mL), filtered
231 through a 0.22 μ m membrane and then, injected (100 μ L loop). Data were analyzed using Astra
232 software version 4.70.

233 **2.11. NMR analyses**

234 NMR spectra (¹H, ¹³C and HSQC-DEPT) from precipitated extracts were obtained using a 400
235 MHz Bruker model Advance III spectrometer with a 5 mm inverse probe. The analyses were
236 performed at 70 °C and the samples (30 mg) were dissolved in Me₂SO-*d*₆. Chemical shifts are
237 expressed in ppm (δ) relative to Me₂SO-*d*₆ at 39.7 (¹³C) and 2.40 (¹H).

238 **2.12. Determination of HMGCR inhibitory activity**

239 The polysaccharide-enriched extracts were solubilized in water (50 mg/mL) and applied (20
240 μ L) into a 96-wells plate. Their inhibitory activity was measured using the commercial HMGCR (3-
241 hydroxy-3-methylglutaryl coenzyme A reductase) activity assay (Sigma-Aldrich, Madrid, Spain)
242 according to the manufacturer's instructions by monitoring their absorbance change (340 nm) at 37
243 $^{\circ}$ C using a 96-wells microplate reader BioTek Sinergy HT (BioTek, Winooski, USA). Pravastatin
244 was used as a control for positive inhibition.

245 **2.13. Macrophage cultures and immunomodulatory testing**

246 The human monocyte THP-1 cell line was obtained from ATCC and cultured with
247 supplemented RPMI 1640 medium (10% fetal bovine serum (FBS), 100 U/mL penicillin, 100
248 mg/mL streptomycin, 2mM L-glutamine and 0.05 mM β -mercaptoethanol). For differentiation into
249 macrophages, THP-1 cells were seeded (5×10^5 cells/mL) in 24 well-plate with 100 ng/mL phorbol
250 12-myristate 13-acetate (PMA) and maintained for 48 h at 37 $^{\circ}$ C under 5% CO₂ in a humidified
251 incubator

252 Firstly, the extracts cytotoxicity was evaluated in differentiated macrophages using 3-(4,5-
253 dimethylthiazol)-2,5-diphenyl tetrazolium bromide (MTT) according to Mosmann (1983).
254 Afterwards, the macrophages were washed with PBS and then replaced with serum-free medium
255 containing LPS (0.05 μ g/mL) and subtoxic concentrations of the shiitake extracts. After 10 h of
256 incubation, cells supernatants were collected and store at -20 $^{\circ}$ C until use.

257 Pro-inflammatory cytokines TNF α (Tumour necrosis factor alpha), IL-1 β (Interleukin 1 beta)
258 and IL-6 (Interleukin 6) were measured in the supernatants by BD Biosciences Human ELISA set
259 (Aalst, Belgium) following the manufacturer's instructions. The quantification was calculated
260 considering positive controls (cells stimulated with LPS) as a 100% cytokine secretion. The colour
261 generated was determined by measuring the OD at 450 nm using a multiscanner autoreader
262 (Sunrise, Tecan). Experiments were carried out in triplicate.

263 **2.14. Statistical analyses**

264 Differences were evaluated at 95% confidence level ($P \leq 0.05$) using a one-way analysis of
265 variance (ANOVA) followed by Tukey's Multiple Comparison test. Statistical analysis was
266 performed using GraphPad Prism version 5.01 (GraphPad Software, San Diego, CA).

267 **3. Results and Discussion**

268 ***3.1. UAE and SWE as individual extraction methodologies***

269 Polysaccharide extractions using ultrasounds or subcritical water were carried out at different
270 extraction times and compared with conventional methodologies such as hot water extractions
271 (HWE). When the obtained yields were evaluated (Table 1), results indicated that SWEs extracted
272 more material from shiitake powder than UAEs, almost 2 fold more than HWEs at any extraction
273 time and also more than a commonly utilized method to isolate polysaccharides using water at
274 120°C for 20 min (SPE) (Jeurink et al., 2008). These results might suggest that the high temperature
275 of the pressurized water (that might have easily penetrated in the hyphae because it still maintains
276 its liquid status) was more effective to dissolve and extract fungal compounds than other methods
277 using lower temperatures such as 120, 100 or 50°C. Similarly, the propagation of ultrasonic waves
278 might have also provided a greater water penetration into the fungal hyphae than more conventional
279 methodologies using higher temperatures.

280 HWE yields were higher than reported in previous studies where extractions were carried out
281 for 60 min at 98 °C (Morales et al., 2018a; Morales et al., 2019). However, the value obtained using
282 the SPE method was in the range of previous works (Jeurink et al., 2008). Worth to notice was the
283 decrease observed on SWEs carried out for more than 45 min. It might indicate clogging of the
284 cellulose filter due to the large amount of extracted material. Therefore, if long extraction periods
285 are required, extraction cycles are encouraged since similar studies but using extraction cycles (200
286 °C, 5 cycles of 5 min) yielded slightly higher values (Palanisamy et al., 2014).

287 The polysaccharides amount detected in UAE obtained fractions (Table 1) were in concordance
288 with previous works where 9.75% polysaccharides were recorded from *L. edodes* after 21 min
289 extraction (Zhao et al., 2018). Similarly, the SWE fractions obtained after 15 min extraction showed

290 a slightly higher polysaccharide content than noticed by Zhang, Yang, Lin, Zhao, & Wang (2019)
291 but because only lower temperatures were tested (11.35 – 12.09%).

292 After extraction, the obtained fractions were submitted to precipitation to generate
293 polysaccharide- enriched extracts (Figure 1). Results indicated that the HWE fractions contained
294 less material susceptible of ethanol precipitation compared with UAE fractions and particularly the
295 SWE fraction obtained after 15 min extraction. This fraction contained the highest polysaccharide
296 levels yielding 15.5 g/100g SWE fraction, levels that were higher than those obtained using other
297 advanced technologies such as UAE after 60 min (10.1 g/100g UAE fraction) or *e.g.* microwave-
298 assisted extraction (MAE) (10.5 g/100 g MAE fraction) (Gil-Ramirez et al., 2019).

299 Total β -glucan content of shiitake and all generated extracts was determined using a
300 commonly used enzymatic method (Gil-Ramirez & Soler-Rivas, 2014). The initial raw powder
301 contained 29% (w/w) β -glucans representing the 69% of the total carbohydrates quantified being
302 chitins in lower concentrations (5.2%). Both values were in concordance with several works
303 (Roncero-Ramos, Mendiola-Lanao, Perez-Clavijo, & Delgado-Andrade, 2017; Morales et al.,
304 2018a; Morales et al., 2019) although they were slightly higher than others (Nitschke et al., 2011;
305 Sari, Prange, Lelley, & Hambitzer, 2017). HWE extracted lower β -glucan amounts than UAE or
306 SWE except for the SWEs carried out during 60 min (Figure 2a). In fact, subcritical water
307 extractions longer than 15 min were detrimental to get β -glucan-enriched fractions, opposite to
308 results obtained after UAE extractions. In the latter case, 60 min extraction yielded fractions with β -
309 glucan concentrations similar to those obtained with only 15 min SWEs. Moreover, HWE extracted
310 from 6 to 9% of the chitins present in shiitake mushrooms and similarly UAE extracted 5 to 15%.
311 Only SWE at 15 min showed the highest recovery (35%). However, since chitins are completely
312 insoluble in water, high recoveries were not expected. The extracted compounds might be derivative
313 products from the chitin hydrolysis or depolymerization induced by high temperatures, pressures
314 and/or ultrasounds as suggested in previous works (Palanisamy et al., 2014; Morales et al., 2018a;
315 Morales et al., 2019). SWEs displayed a significant decrease in chitin yield (Figure 2b) similar to
316 those recorded for β -glucans. It might indicate that extraction time was excessive and therefore the

317 filters from the extraction cell were blocked and no proper extraction was made. However, it might
318 also suggest that the excessive time at 200°C induced hydrolysis and degradation of these two kinds
319 of polysaccharides into lower molecular weight products that were not precipitated as
320 polysaccharides in the analyzed extracts.

321 In order to test whether the different utilized extraction methodologies showed certain
322 structure selectivity, the β -glucan contents were also evaluated using two additional methods
323 developed to detect (1 \rightarrow 3)- or (1 \rightarrow 3),(1 \rightarrow 6)- β -glucans (Ko & Lin, 2004; Nitschke et al., 2011). The
324 amounts of extracted β -glucans were slightly different depending on the methodology utilized *e.g.*
325 after 15 min, HWE and SWE yielded fractions with similar (1 \rightarrow 3)- β -glucan concentrations (Figure
326 3a), however, in the SWE fraction 84% of them were pointed as (1 \rightarrow 3),(1 \rightarrow 6)- β -glucans while the
327 HWE fraction apparently contained only 21% of β -glucans with (1 \rightarrow 6) (Figure 3b). Similarly, after
328 60 min extraction, UAE fractions showed lower (1 \rightarrow 3)- β -glucans than HWE fractions but most of
329 them were detected as (1 \rightarrow 3),(1 \rightarrow 6)- β -glucans, reaching levels similar to SWE fractions extracted
330 for 15 min. These results suggested that HWE was extracting more linear glucans than SWE or
331 UAE as linear β -glucans are usually bound by (1 \rightarrow 3)- β -linkages while SWE or UAE extracted more
332 branched (1 \rightarrow 3),(1 \rightarrow 6)- β -glucans. However, branched glucans are more soluble and therefore they
333 are easily extractable while the linear (1 \rightarrow 3)- β -glucans remain firmly attached to the fungal cell
334 wall, requiring stronger extraction methods. For this reason, SWE or UAE were expected to extract
335 more linear glucans than milder treatments (HWE). An explanation for this could be that the (1 \rightarrow 3)-
336 β -glucans obtained with HWE presented lower molecular weight being consequently more soluble
337 than those glucans extracted with SWE or UAE (as noticed with HPSEC, see later). Moreover, a
338 quantitative mismatch was also noticed between the values obtained with the enzymatic method
339 calculating the total β -glucan content and the fluorimetric/colorimetric determinations. For instance,
340 SWE (15 min) fractions contained 27.1 g/100g total β -glucans (Figure 2) but only 9% of them
341 exhibited fluorescence indicating the presence of β -(1 \rightarrow 3) linkage (Figure 3a) and 7% of them were
342 detected by the colorimetric method as (1 \rightarrow 3), (1 \rightarrow 6)- β -glucans (Figure 3b). But, according to
343 previous publications most of the β -glucans present in shiitake mushrooms showed β -(1 \rightarrow 3),(1 \rightarrow 6)

344 structures such as for instance lentinan (Nitschke et al., 2011) thus, these determined percentages
345 were too low for a main component. Moreover, the SWE fraction obtained after 15 min contained
346 only 15.5 g/100 g polysaccharides (Table 1) and 2.5 g of them were pointed as chitins (Figure 2b).
347 These observations might indicated that selected extraction technologies were extracting more
348 polysaccharides than noticed or that the enzymatic determination might overestimate the total β -
349 glucan concentration. Other reports also noticed significantly lower β -glucans values in *L. edodes*
350 when fluorimetric methods were utilized compared to the enzymatic procedure (Gründemann et al.,
351 2015). Therefore, the use of indirect colorimetric/fluorimetric determinations should never be
352 considered (in complex mixtures as these extracts) as a precise determination method since their
353 sensitivity might be influenced by the presence of many interference compounds as suggested for
354 the fluorimetric determination (Gil-Ramirez et al., 2019). Thus, in order to define the fraction
355 compositions more precise analytical tools were utilized.

356 ***3.2. Combining extraction methodologies***

357 Individual extractions indicated that SWE carried out during 15 min and UAE during 60 min
358 were adequate to extract more β -glucans than either HWE or SPE methods. However, shiitake
359 contained approx. 34.3% polysaccharides and they were not all extracted. Thus, combination of
360 both technologies UAE+SWE were tested to improve the β -glucan content of obtained fractions.
361 Moreover, a pretreatment of the shiitake raw material with supercritical CO₂ was also tested
362 because on the one hand, CO₂ generates an acid environment that might enhance cell structures
363 breakdown and on the other hand, it extract lipid compounds that are within the mushroom dry
364 matter (chitins and β -glucans). The latter consequence combined with the high pressure used during
365 SFE might alter cell wall structure facilitating its disruption and the extraction of structural
366 polysaccharides. Therefore, pretreated (SFE) material was submitted to UAE or SWE selecting the
367 optimal extraction times.

368 The three tested combinations of extracting methods showed very high yields (Table 1), almost
369 doubling those obtained with individual extractions, particularly UAE+SWE. However, not all the

370 extracted material precipitated afterwards and they were not all polysaccharides. Combination of
371 UAE+SWE showed results similar to SFE+SWE, apparently both pre-treatments facilitates the
372 subsequent SWE extracting approx. 31% more polysaccharides than only SWE. SFE pre-treatment
373 also improved approx. 41% the polysaccharide levels obtained in UAE fractions although they still
374 contained less than UAE+SWE or SFE+SWE fractions. The combinations were more effective than
375 SPE methods (5.1%) or other extraction technologies used to obtain polysaccharides-enriched
376 fractions such as MAE (10.5%) (Gil-Ramirez et al., 2019).

377 Apparently, UAE+SWE or SFE+SWE extracted almost all the carbohydrates present in the
378 mushroom (Table 2) and according to the enzymatic protocol they also managed to extract all the β -
379 glucans yielding fractions containing approx. 35% β -glucans. However, the results from the
380 fluorimetric method indicated that shiitake contained 10.4% (1 \rightarrow 3)- β -glucans and the combination
381 of methodologies extracted slightly less compounds yielding fractions with up to 8% (1 \rightarrow 3)- β -
382 glucans. The combination SFE+UAE was in this case more adequate to concentrate this type of
383 compounds on fractions including up to 9% (1 \rightarrow 3)- β -glucans where one third of them were
384 (1 \rightarrow 3),(1 \rightarrow 6)- β -glucans. In fact, the three combinations extracted similar concentrations of
385 (1 \rightarrow 3),(1 \rightarrow 6)- β -glucans but they all generated fractions that contained more β -glucans than
386 individual extractions. The differences between the selected combinations were more pronounced in
387 their capacity to extract chitin-derivatives compounds. UAE+SWE extracted almost 83% of the
388 chitins detected in the mushroom yielding fractions with more than 5% chitin-derivatives.
389 SFE+SWE were less effective and significantly different than SFE+UAE that extracted even less
390 derivatives. Comparing to other technologies, chitins were present in MAE extracts in approx. 2%
391 (Smiderle et al., 2017) therefore, the pretreatment with SFE or UAE particularly before SWE
392 seemed to be a more interesting protocol to extract β -glucans and soluble chitins-derivatives than
393 application of individual extraction methodologies, probably because they both facilitate the
394 disruption of the material for a subsequent subcritical water extraction.

395 However, similar quantitative discrepancies between the enzymatic and the fluorimetric
396 determinations were detected as noticed within the fractions obtained with individual extractions.

397 Thus, the enzymatic method was carried out using 100% starch and schizophyllan as respectively
398 (1→4),(1→6)- α and (1→3),(1→6)- β -glucan standards and mixed as 50% starch:sea sand, 50%
399 starch:schizophyllan and 50% schizophyllan:sea sand (w/w). Results indicated that, when only β -
400 glucans were present in the mixtures, quantitative determinations were accurate (only 7% error) but,
401 the amount of α -glucans was underestimated particularly when mixed with schizophyllan inducing
402 a β -glucan overestimation (approx. 14.2%) since the amount of β -glucans is calculated by
403 subtracting the α -glucan levels to the total glucan concentration. Therefore, the enzymatic,
404 fluorimetric or colorimetric methods should be only used for preliminary assessment and more
405 precise determinations were carried out in order to identify the compounds present in the obtained
406 fractions.

407 ***3.3. Chemical composition of the obtained fractions***

408 The monosaccharide composition of the polysaccharide-enriched extracts obtained with
409 individual and combined extraction technologies was analyzed by GC-MS. Results pointed out the
410 presence of mannose, galactose, and glucose, being the latter in high levels (Table 3). Higher
411 extraction periods led to higher amounts of glucose in HWE extracts, while the glucose content of
412 UAE extracts (and of the other two monosaccharides) was almost independent of the extraction
413 time. The glucose levels were in concordance with β -glucan determinations, *e.g.* SWE extracted
414 higher β -glucan amounts at 15 min than at longer extraction times as well as higher glucose levels.
415 UAE+SWE extracts showed higher glucose levels than UAE but similar to SWE extracts suggesting
416 that probably with the first extraction (UAE) only part of the glucans were extracted and in the
417 second extraction an approximately 20 % more was further extracted to yield the same values as
418 with SWE alone. Heteropolymers including mannose and galactose in their structure are usually
419 easily water-soluble since they are weakly attached to other molecules from the fungal matrix
420 (Smiderle et al., 2008). HWE extracts obtained with short extraction times showed higher levels of
421 mannose than longer extractions. On the contrary, SWE extracts (15 min) contained lower mannose
422 and lower galactose contents, being glucose more concentrated suggesting that SWE might show
423 certain specificity to isolate β -glucans than other heteropolymers. UAE extracts showed higher

424 levels of mannose and galactose and lower glucose than SWE (15 min), suggesting a more
425 heterogeneous composition than the SWE extract. The use of SFE pretreatment slightly enhanced
426 the β -glucan selectivity noticed for SWE since SFE+SWE extracts showed a slightly higher
427 percentage of glucose and lower galactose levels. This combination was more specific than
428 UAE+SWE where more mannose and less glucose was noticed.

429 The different monosaccharide composition noticed depending on the extraction methodology
430 utilized suggested the presence of different polymers, therefore, the extracts were also analyzed by
431 HPSEC. Results showed heterogeneous elution profiles (Supplementary figure S1) confirming the
432 presence of polysaccharides with different molecular mass. Similar profiles were observed for HWE
433 extracts obtained at different extraction times (Fig. S1a). UAE extracts obtained after 60 min
434 extractions were also slightly different than the other extracts obtained at shorter extraction times
435 (Fig S1b) but differences were more pronounced for SWE extracts. Those fractions obtained after
436 15 min extraction showed a peak with maximum at approx. 57 min indicating the presence of
437 medium molecular weight compounds (Fig. S1c). With increasing extraction times, their profile
438 shifted to other peaks with maxima approx. at 60 min indicating the presence of lower molecular
439 weight compounds and therefore, suggesting degradation provoked by the large extraction method.
440 UAE+SWE and SFE+SWE extracts showed a profile similar to SWE extracts while in SFE+UAE
441 extracts seemed to increase the amount of high molecular weight compounds (R.T. approx. 45 min)
442 compared to UAE extracts. The high molecular weight compounds noticed in UAE-related extracts
443 were lacking in SWE extracts suggesting that the polymers extracted with SWE showed a more
444 narrow size distribution (medium molecular weight) while UAE-related extracts contained a more
445 heterogeneous size distribution.

446 Moreover, to identify the compounds present in polysaccharide-enriched extracts from the
447 individual and combined extraction methodologies, NMR studies were carried out and compared
448 with literature data (Supplementary figure S2). The extracts contained a mixture of polysaccharides,
449 including α - and β -glucans and a heteropolymer composed of mannose and galactose (Abreu et al.,
450 2019; de Jesus et al., 2018; Smiderle et al., 2008). Although samples were precipitated with cold

451 ethanol, trehalose signals were observed (δ 92.9/4.82 ppm and 92.6/4.81 ppm). Trehalose is a
452 disaccharide, also known as mycose, and that is commonly found in large amounts in mushrooms.
453 This sugar was also detected in *Pleurotus ostreatus* extracts obtained by SWE in previous works
454 (Smiderle et al., 2017) and could be removed from the polysaccharide fractions after performing
455 dialysis (data not shown).

456 Intense signals relative to C-1 of α -D-Glcp (δ 99.3-99.5/4.97-4.98) and to C-3 *O*-substituted (δ
457 82.8-82.9/3.54-3.55) were observed, suggesting the presence of (1 \rightarrow 3)- α -glucan structures, that
458 were also previously reported and isolated from other mushrooms such as *Fomitopsis betulina* (de
459 Jesus et al., 2018). Moreover, the extracts showed intense ^{13}C signals arising at 102.4-103.7 ppm
460 and ^1H signals at 4.14-4.44 ppm confirming the presence of C-1 of glucans in β -configuration (Liu
461 et al., 2014), as well as signals at the range of δ 85.8-87.0 (^{13}C) and at δ 3.23-3.39 (^1H) related to C-
462 3 *O*-substituted. In addition, inverted signals at δ 68.1-68.5/3.89-3.99 and δ 68.1-68.5/3.37-3.50
463 confirmed CH_2 *O*-substitution of the same units, being in the concordance with the scientific
464 literature, where the mainly studied glucan from shiitake mushrooms is a branched (1 \rightarrow 3)(1 \rightarrow 6)- β -
465 glucan.

466 Small intensity signals of α -D-Galp were observed in almost all spectra at 98.4-98.6/4.63-4.65
467 ppm as well as signals of β -D-Manp at δ 101.1-101.5/4.82-4.84 ppm, being in concordance with the
468 results of monosaccharide composition and suggesting the existence of a heteropolymer consisting
469 of galactose and mannose.

470 According to these results, it was possible to observe that the polysaccharide-enriched fractions
471 obtained from different extraction methods presented similar polysaccharide composition: (1 \rightarrow 3)- α -
472 glucans, (1 \rightarrow 3)(1 \rightarrow 6)- β -glucans, and a heteropolymer composed of mannose and galactose. The
473 main difference among them seemed to be the proportion of each polysaccharide extracted.

474 **3.4. Biological activities of the obtained extracts**

475 The production of β -glucan-enriched fractions should be encouraged for the production of
476 functional foods because fungal β -glucans are biologically active molecules with many interesting

477 biological activities. However, their beneficial properties can be influenced by their extraction
478 procedure since some of them might modify the tridimensional structure of the polymer (Benito-
479 Roman et al., 2016b). Therefore, the hypocholesterolemic and immunomodulatory activities of the
480 precipitated extracts with the highest β -glucan contents were selected to evaluate whether after the
481 extraction treatments, they still maintain their biological activities.

482 Water soluble extracts from several mushrooms including soluble β -glucans were able to inhibit
483 the key enzyme of the cholesterol metabolism (Gil-Ramirez et al., 2017), therefore, obtained
484 extracts were tested as HMGCR (3-hydroxy-3-methylglutaryl coenzyme A reductase) inhibitors.
485 Results indicated that SFE+UAE and SFE+SWE extracts showed inhibitory capacity similar to 0.5
486 mg/mL pravastatin, the statin utilized as positive control (Table 4). The UAE+SWE extract
487 exhibited a slightly lower capacity. The combination of these two extraction methodologies seemed
488 to generate extracts with lower inhibitors concentration or to be slightly detrimental for the structure
489 of the HMGCR inhibitors but still, it was better combination than HWE where half of the inhibitory
490 activity was lost. Gil-Ramirez et al. (2013a) studied the HMGCR inhibitory activity of SWE
491 extracts obtained from *L. edodes* and indicated that extracts obtained at 150 °C (5 cycles 5 min)
492 showed less inhibitory activity than similar extracts obtained at 25°C probably because the
493 inhibitors were thermal sensitive. However, SFE+SWE or UAE+SWE extracts still retained very
494 high inhibitory activity. Perhaps, the pre-treatment with UAE or SFE prior to SWE
495 protected/modulated the inhibitors structure making them more active or less susceptible to thermal
496 degradation or perhaps, the *L. edodes* strain was different than the one utilized in the previous work
497 as differences between varieties or cultivation methods seemed to influence their inhibitory
498 properties too (Gil-Ramirez et al., 2013a).

499 The immunomodulatory activities of the extracts obtained with combined methodologies were
500 also tested as their capacity to reduce the secretion of pro-inflammatory cytokines in macrophages
501 differentiated from THP-1 human monocytes cell line. The preliminary experiments to assess the
502 extract cytotoxicity indicated that when applied up to 200 μ g/mL viability of THP-1 macrophages
503 was not affected (data not shown). Thus, the immunomodulatory activity was tested in two subtoxic

504 concentrations (100 and 200 µg/mL). The THP-1 macrophages stimulated with LPS (positive
505 control) exhibited a significant release of the three pro-inflammatory cytokines studied (1295
506 pg/mL TNF α , 4586 pg/mL IL-1 β and 1837 pg/mL IL-6) compared to non-stimulated cells
507 (negative control) (Figure 4). Addition of the extracts obtained with combined methodologies
508 significantly reduced the amount of TNF α liberated in the media. When applied at the highest tested
509 concentration a 24 to 32% reduction in TNF α was noticed (down to 883 pg/mL in the case of
510 SFE+UAE), however, the extract obtained after 60 min HWE did not effectively modulate any
511 response. SFE+UAE seemed to be more effective because it induced the mentioned TNF α reduction
512 and was the only extract inducing a 25% reduction (3462 pg/mL) in IL-1 β secretion when applied at
513 200 µg/mL. The IL-6 release was also inhibited approx. 25% by SFE+UAE and SFE+SWE (1420
514 and 1343 pg/mL, respectively) extracts being the latter also significantly effective when applied at
515 lower concentration. However, SWE extracts obtained from *L. edodes* at 50 °C (5 cycles 5 min)
516 reduced approx. 90% the release of IL-6, IL-1 β and 20% TNF α while if the temperature was higher
517 (200 °C) only a slight reduction in IL-6 was noticed (Gil-Ramirez et al., 2013b). Thus, the
518 temperature utilized in the production of the SFE+SWE extract could have impaired their beneficial
519 immunomodulatory properties. Thus, SFE+UAE was a more adequate combination of
520 methodologies to maintain the immunomodulatory properties since its extract could reduce the
521 liberation of all pro-inflammatory cytokines tested but, their activity might be influenced by the
522 temperature utilized.

523 **4. Conclusion**

524 In conclusion, submission of shiitake mushrooms to UAE or SFE followed by UAE or SWE
525 were more effective methods to obtain β -glucan-enriched fractions than individual UAE or SWE
526 extractions. The generated fractions contained approx. 20% polysaccharides although according to
527 enzymatic determinations they included approx. 34% β -glucans. Fluorimetric/colorimetric methods
528 pointed out lower amounts of (1 \rightarrow 3) and (1 \rightarrow 3),(1 \rightarrow 6) linked β -glucans. These discrepancies might
529 be caused because they were determined by indirect rough methods that should be considered as

530 preliminary estimations. More accurate analytical methods indicated that UAE fractions contained
531 more heterogenic composition (more mannose and galactose and less glucose contents) and
532 polymers of higher molecular weight than SWE (15 min) or SFE+SWE fractions. UEA-related
533 extracts (*e.g.* 60 min or SFE+UAE, etc.) also extracted lower chitin-derivative contents than SWE-
534 related extracts (15 min, UAE+SWE, SFE+SWE, etc). However, the main differences among the
535 fractions seemed to be the extracted polysaccharides ratio since they all contained (1→3)- α -glucans,
536 (1→3),(1→6)- β -glucans, and heteropolymers composed of mannose and galactose. Moreover, the
537 obtained fractions might be of interest to design functional foods with hypocholesterolemic
538 properties since they showed high HMGCR inhibitory activity, even higher than other reported
539 extracts obtained at high temperatures similar to those used in SFE+SWE or SFE+UAE (Gil-
540 Ramirez et al., 2013a). But, the immunomodulatory properties of the extracted β -glucans might be
541 compromised because although they were still able to reduce secretion of TNF α , IL-1 β and IL-6 in
542 macrophage cell lines, only the SFE+UAE fractions managed to reduce them approx. 20% while
543 other extracts obtained using SWE at lower temperatures were reported more effective (Gil-
544 Ramirez et al., 2013b).

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549 **Declaration of interest**

550 None.

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Table captions

Table 1. Extraction yields, polysaccharides and other carbohydrates contents obtained in the fractions extracted from shiitake using individual and combined extraction technologies. Different letters (a-g) denote significant differences ($P < 0.05$). *Calculated by subtracting total polysaccharide levels to the total carbohydrate values from the extracted fractions obtained before polysaccharide precipitation

Table 2. Carbohydrates determined in shiitake powder and the fractions obtained by SPE and combined technologies (UAE+SWE, SFE+UAE and SFE+SWE). Different letters (a-d) denote significant differences ($P < 0.05$) between values of the same column.

Table 3. Monosaccharide composition (%) of the precipitated extracts obtained from shiitake by the different individual and combined technologies.

Table 4. HMGCR inhibitory activity (%) of the obtained precipitated extracts obtained by HWE during 60 min (HWE60') and combination of advanced methodologies. Different letters (a-c) denote significant differences ($P < 0.05$) between samples.

Figure captions

Figure 1. Extraction workflow followed to obtain different fractions and extracts from shiitake powder. Continuous line indicate single extractions and dotted lines indicate the order followed when two technologies were combined. (SPE, steam pressurized extraction; SFE, supercritical fluid extraction; UAE, ultrasound assisted-extraction; SWE, subcritical water extraction).

Figure 2. Total β -glucan (a) and chitin (b) content in the fractions obtained after HWE, UAE and SWE from shiitake mushrooms. Different letters denote significant statistical differences ($P < 0.05$) between fractions obtained by the same extraction technology at different times (A-D) and obtained by different extraction technologies at the same time (a-c).

Figure 3. Content of (a) (1 \rightarrow 3)- β -glucans and (b) (1 \rightarrow 3),(1 \rightarrow 6)- β -glucans in the fractions obtained after HWE, UAE and SWE from shiitake mushrooms. Different letters denote significant statistical differences ($P < 0.05$) between fractions obtained by the same extraction technology at different times (A-B) and obtained by different extraction technologies at the same time (a-c).

Figure 4. Levels of a) TNF α , b) IL-1 β and c) IL-6 secreted by THP-1/M activated with LPS in presence of HWE (60 min), UAE+SWE, SFE+UAE and SFE+SWE extracts. Positive control: cells stimulated with LPS but in absence of extract. Negative control: non LPS-activated cells. Different letters (a-c) denote significant differences ($P < 0.05$) between samples.

Table 1.

Technology	Extraction time (min)	Yield of extracted matter/ 100 g shiitake (% w/w)	Yield of precipitated matter/ 100 g extracted fraction (% w/w)	Yield of precipitated matter/ 100 g shiitake (% w/w)	Total polysaccharides in extracted fractions (g/100g)	Other carbohydrates in extracted fractions (g/100g)*
Hot water extraction (HWE)	15	37.99±5.35 ^{de}	20.29±2.88 ^e	7.71±1.09 ^e	5.02±0.71 ^c	9.63
	30	34.58±2.22 ^e	19.76±1.20 ^e	6.83±0.41 ^e	4.56±0.27 ^c	18.49
	45	39.96±0.06 ^{de}	21.18±0.30 ^{de}	8.46±0.12 ^e	4.02±0.06 ^c	30.09
	60	31.24±0.90 ^e	16.59±0.52 ^{ef}	5.18±0.16 ^e	4.78±0.15 ^c	41.79
Ultrasound-assisted extraction (UAE)	15	45.74±1.42 ^d	27.26±0.60 ^d	12.47±0.27 ^g	8.59±1.41 ^{bc}	13.74
	30	56.19±2.81 ^c	30.90±0.76 ^{cd}	17.36±0.43 ^e	9.37±2.92 ^{bc}	21.04
	45	58.52±2.22 ^c	30.92±1.95 ^{cd}	18.09±1.14 ^e	7.76±1.31 ^c	29.73
	60	60.36±1.48 ^c	34.56±3.17 ^c	20.86±1.91 ^e	10.14±2.46 ^{bc}	36.50
Subcritical water extraction (SWE)	15	73.21±0.91 ^{ab}	52.88±2.12 ^b	38.71±1.55 ^e	15.54±2.18 ^{ab}	12.85
	30	75.31±0.91 ^{ab}	23.16±0.56 ^{de}	17.44±0.42 ^e	6.80±0.94 ^c	31.64
	45	70.58±3.82 ^b	26.96±0.99 ^{de}	19.03±0.70 ^e	7.93±1.07 ^c	32.51
	60	64.49±2.62 ^{bc}	20.05±1.32 ^e	12.93±0.85 ^f	5.92±0.67 ^c	27.79
Steam pressurized extraction (SPE)	20	37.96±0.16 ^{de}	11.42±0.01 ^f	4.34±0.01 ^g	5.13±0.01 ^c	10.16
UAE+SWE	60 + 15	81.20±1.06 ^a	68.88±2.33 ^a	55.93±1.89 ^a	21.14±1.96 ^a	37.97
SFE+UAE	180 + 60	59.73±0.44 ^c	49.42±2.66 ^b	29.52±1.59 ^d	14.46±1.97 ^b	34.46
SFE+SWE	180 + 15	74.95±1.26 ^{ab}	63.54±1.75 ^a	47.62±1.31 ^b	19.88±1.23 ^{ab}	39.27

*Calculated by subtracting total polysaccharide levels to the total carbohydrate values from the extracted fractions obtained before polysaccharide precipitation

Table 2.

Sample	Total carbohydrates		Total β -glucans		(1 \rightarrow 3)- β -glucans		(1 \rightarrow 3),(1 \rightarrow 6)- β -glucans		Chitins	
	g / 100 g fraction	g / 100 g shiitake	g / 100 g fraction	g / 100 g shiitake	g / 100 g fraction	g / 100 g shiitake	g / 100 g fraction	g / 100 g shiitake	g / 100 g fraction	g / 100 g shiitake
Shiitake powder	-	42.10 \pm 1.17 ^a	-	28.85 \pm 0.43 ^a	-	10.40 \pm 0.22 ^a	-	3.22 \pm 0.01 ^a	-	5.19 \pm 0.13 ^a
SPEmethod	15.29 \pm 3.33 ^b	5.80 \pm 1.26 ^c	6.32 \pm 0.29 ^b	2.40 \pm 0.11 ^d	2.94 \pm 0.01 ^b	1.12 \pm 0.01 ^c	0.50 \pm 0.01 ^b	0.19 \pm 0.01 ^c	1.07 \pm 0.09 ^d	0.41 \pm 0.03 ^e
UAE+SWE	59.11 \pm 1.22 ^a	47.99 \pm 0.99 ^a	35.97 \pm 0.43 ^a	29.21 \pm 0.35 ^a	8.33 \pm 0.18 ^a	6.76 \pm 0.15 ^b	2.50 \pm 0.32 ^a	2.03 \pm 0.26 ^b	5.30 \pm 0.18 ^a	4.30 \pm 0.15 ^b
SFE+UAE	48.92 \pm 3.43 ^a	29.22 \pm 2.05 ^b	32.17 \pm 0.28 ^a	19.22 \pm 0.17 ^c	9.09 \pm 0.94 ^a	5.43 \pm 0.56 ^b	3.03 \pm 0.24 ^a	1.81 \pm 0.14 ^b	3.86 \pm 0.05 ^c	2.31 \pm 0.03 ^d
SFE+SWE	59.15 \pm 5.23 ^a	44.33 \pm 3.91 ^a	34.82 \pm 0.32 ^a	26.10 \pm 0.24 ^b	8.12 \pm 0.66 ^a	6.09 \pm 0.49 ^b	2.51 \pm 0.14 ^a	1.88 \pm 0.10 ^b	4.76 \pm 0.14 ^b	3.57 \pm 0.10 ^c

Table 3.

Technology	Extraction time (min)	Monosaccharides (%)		
		Mannose	Glucose	Galactose
Hot water extraction (HWE)	15	21.9	68.6	9.5
	30	16.1	71.2	12.7
	45	9.3	81.5	9.2
	60	9.2	81.3	9.5
Ultrasound-assisted extraction (UAE)	15	22.3	62.0	15.7
	30	22.2	61.8	16.0
	45	22.8	62.9	14.3
	60	24.3	63.1	12.6
Subcritical water extraction (SWE)	15	10.4	83.9	5.7
	30	12.2	82.1	5.7
	45	25.0	68.5	6.5
	60	26.5	63.9	9.6
Steam Pressurized extraction (SPE)	20	13.6	74.0	12.4
UAE+SWE	60+15	12.2	82.8	5.0
SFE+UAE	180+60	11.4	81.4	7.2
SFE+SWE	180+15	10.0	85.3	4.7

Table 4.

Sample	HMGCR inhibition (%)
HWE60'	42.52±0.01 ^c
UAE+SWE	84.41±6.98 ^b
SFE+UAE	89.03±0.48 ^{ab}
SFE+SWE	87.32±1.89 ^{ab}
Pravastatin	99.21±0.36 ^a

Figure 1.

Figure 2.

Figure 3.

Figure 4.

Supplementary material:

Figure S1. HPSEC elution profiles of a) HWE, b) UAE and c) SWE fractions obtained at different extraction times (15 to 60 min) and d) SPE and combined fractions.

Figure S2. HSQC-DEPT35 NMR spectra of extracts obtained after a) HWE 60 min, b) UAE 60 min, c) SWE 15 min, d) UAE+SWE, e) SFE+UAE and f) SFE+SWE. Experiments were performed in DMSO at 70 °C (chemical shifts are expressed in δ ppm).

Supplementary figure 1 (S1).

Supplementary figure 2 (S2).

